

CHARTER INFOGRAPHIC

CHARTER Deliverable D7.9

Grant Agreement Number: 869471

Project Acronym: CHARTER

Project title: Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity

Starting Date: 01/08/2020

Project Duration: 48 months

Project Officer: Alberto Zocchi

Project Coordinator: Bruce Forbes / LAY

Leading Author: Coordination team / LAY

Contributing partners: -

Co-financed by the Connecting Europe Facility of the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

CHARTER INFOGRAPHIC and other outreach tools

CHARTER Deliverable 7.9

Version 2 (revised after the first review)

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Authors: CHARTER coordination team / LAY

Due Submission Date: 31/07/2021

Actual Submission Date: 30/08/2021

Revised version submitted: 30/06/2022

Status	
Draft	
Final	x

Type		
R	Document, report	x
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	
OTHER		

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Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (incl. the Commission services)	

Revision history

Date(s)	Lead author(s)	Comments
15.8.2021	Philip Burgess	1 st draft version
30.8.2021	CHARTER coordination team	Final version, submitted
30.6.2022	CHARTER coordination team	Final version (v2), revised according the comments given during the first review, submitted

Introduction - CHARTER outreach tools

The CHARTER project completed a number of distinct outreach materials during 2021. Some were self-contained and designed as an introduction and overview of the project and its goals. These include a conference sized poster, a full-size rollup and an online infographic.

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CHARTER project rollup

The full-sized CHARTER project rollup was created by the project office for use as needed at conferences, presentations and anywhere where a desk or stand existed to deliver information about the CHARTER project. The rollup is located at the project office in Rovaniemi and is used as needed locally or when travelling.

CHARTER

DRIVERS AND FEEDBACKS OF CHANGES IN ARCTIC TERRESTRIAL BIODIVERSITY

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Goal: To advance the adaptive capacity of Arctic communities to climatic and biodiversity changes through state-of-the-art synthesis based on data collection, analysis and modelling of Arctic change with major socio-economic implications and feedbacks.

- 21 research institutions
- 9 countries
- Over 70 researchers
- Multiple academic disciplines, local and indigenous peoples
- Engages People & Science and Policy Makers

charter-arctic.org

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CHARTER Project Infographic

The CHARTER project has created a visual online infographic which is hosted in the cloud (in this case Prezi) which is also embedded on the landing page of the CHARTER project website. It is also embeddable to any other website should the need arise.

The infographic walks the viewer through the cross-cutting needs for a multidisciplinary approach to the complex issues facing the Arctic region. Then in a user controlled navigable image based graphic, the goals and aims of the CHARTER project are outlined. The structure of the project is also outlined and the partners and institutions are shown. The infographic is launchable from the landing page of the CHARTER website and is also viewable on the Prezi website here:

<https://prezi.com/view/gqDjTrtNES3Mt4hLVUyg/>

